

IMPROVEMENT FACTORS OF FINE ARTS AND TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION CURRICULUM

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Abstract: This article describes the formation and development of students' visual artistic and creative abilities, their thoughts and impressions, and their creativity through visual art and technological education classes. Also, the methods of creating a foundation for them to use the theoretical knowledge and practical skills they have acquired in the subject of visual arts in the lessons of the subject of technology, as well as the necessary recommendations related to the field, are presented.

Keywords: aesthetic perception of visual, applied and architectural works of art, develops visual memory, creative imagination, aesthetic and emotional sensitivity, composite culture, natural and abandoned materials.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the comprehensive modernization processes, which are being rapidly implemented in the socio-economic and cultural-educational spheres, as well as in all aspects, have an effective effect on all stages of the continuous education system. is doing. As a result, as an important description of the competitive new modern educational environment and a condition for the successful realization of the possibilities of the student's personality related to visual art and technological creativity - with special attention to the unique creative activities of students in educational processes. further improvement requires the development of solutions to all problems in its existing components.

We know that visual arts and technological education are of great importance in educating students in an artistic and aesthetic spirit, and are extremely important in the implementation of ideological-political, mental and physical, moral and labor education of students. is important.

In addition, during the lessons of visual art and technological education, students acquire special knowledge, skills and abilities related to the field, the existence that surrounds us, visual, practical and architectural art. they learn to perceive their works aesthetically, which develops their thinking ability, visual memory, and creative imagination. As a result, the technological education of students effectively helps to develop their creative abilities and worldview in academic subjects. It improves the personality of the student in all aspects.

The following can be included among the special tasks of the academic discipline of fine arts and technological education:

- it is necessary to develop an aesthetic attitude towards existence, things and events around us in students, to teach them to be able to feel and understand the beauty of existence and art, as well as to actively apply these feelings and concepts to the current life;
- it is necessary to rapidly develop the manifestations of artistic and national culture and the understanding of their importance in the life of our society;

- it is permissible to develop aesthetic and emotional sensitivities;
- it is necessary to actively form artistic and practical skills;
- it is necessary to give students knowledge about the basics of real drawing, to create a lot of skills and competencies in drawing a picture according to the object itself, drawing from memory and imagination;
- it is necessary to develop perception, color perception, composite culture, spatial broad thinking, rich fantasy, clear imagination and combination through vision, solving the given creative tasks in clear images;
- in-depth introduction to the specific features of applied decorative arts, regular training of students' creative abilities, their artistic taste and imagination in all educational lessons of visual arts and technological education subjects it is necessary to focus on cleaning;
- it is necessary to educate students to have an active emotional perception of visual, practical and architectural works of art, to increase their interest in art and to love it;
- it is permissible to teach how to artistically build and make various toys from cardboard and various colored papers, natural and discarded materials;
- it is necessary to develop their technical-creative skills by teaching them to make art based on drawings and pictures of moving toys, various layouts and models.

It should also be noted that one of the main tasks of visual arts and technological education is to provide students with aesthetic, especially artistic education. Therefore, aesthetic education is the education of students' ability to fully perceive the beauties of life, nature, art, and human relationships, and to cultivate creativity based on the laws of beauty. For example, beauty affects the mind, heart, and will of people and enriches their spiritual world.

Also, another important aspect of the lessons of visual arts and technological education is their effectiveness in developing students' artistic creativity. Because an aesthetic attitude to life is the basis of inspiration, it helps to turn work into a source of joy and spirituality.

In fact, in the process of aesthetic education, students' views, feelings, and tastes are formed and developed. This formation, in turn, is closely related to the well-developed ideological and political education and creative thinking.

Today, as one of the main tasks of general secondary education schools, not only understanding existence in students as the need and ability for creative mastery, but also the broad meaning of educating the sense of reconstruction of existence based on the laws of beauty it is necessary to understand. It is important for everyone to be able to see and understand beauty and elegance, no matter what field they work in. In order to educate students artistically and aesthetically, the teacher shows them the subtle beauties of nature, the variety of shapes and colors in it. The beauty of nature, indescribable combinations of colors, which gave students endless joy and excitement, will remain in their memory for a long time. By drawing a picture of the landscape, trees, leaves and flowers on their own, and studying their unique aspects, students will become more familiar and interested in nature. Such lessons help students to see the world and existence in a wide and comprehensive way, as well as to expand their imagination through the rich impressions they get through seeing, and to form a clear and complete understanding of things and events. In the activity of drawing, students carefully study the shape, proportion, position in space, color, and proportions of objects, and this technological education helps students in creative activities in

the educational processes of the subject. very effective. Because they use the theoretical knowledge they have acquired during the lesson on making an object in their practical activities.

It should also be said that visual arts and technological education lessons increase students' perception of existence by seeing it. By the development of visual perception, in most cases, we understand the ability to observe, that is, to compare things and events, to distinguish between their differences and common aspects, as well as their appearance. The results of recent scientific research show that people receive more than 90% of any information they receive from the outside by looking. This shows that the importance of vision in people's life is incomparably great, and it requires the development of all educational and educational activities related to eye activity. Visual art has great potential in developing visual memory in general secondary schools. Therefore, the role of fine art in people's lives becomes clearer.

In conclusion, it can be said that a number of educational and educational tasks are carried out by teaching visual arts and technological education subjects in general secondary schools. Effective implementation of these tasks allows for the broad development of students' thinking, it can be said that it summarizes and deepens their existing understanding of existence and surroundings.

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